

Chelate Formation between Gallium (III) and 3'-Sulpho-2',6'-dichloro-3,3'-dimethyl-4-hydroxyfuchson-5,5'-dicarboxylic Acid. Studies on the Composition, Stability, and Analytical Applications of the Chelate*

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The formation of a red-coloured chelate between trivalent gallium and 3'-sulpho-2', 6'-dichloro-3,3'-dimethyl-4-hydroxyfuchson-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (CAS) with maximum absorption at 550 m μ has been studied. The composition of the chelate has been determined by three methods. The chelate has a composition of 1:1 and is stable at pH 3.0—5.0. The stability constant of the chelate has been calculated by four different methods (a-d). The values of log *K* at 25° are respectively (a) 4.4 $\pm$ 0.1, (b) 4.5 $\pm$ 0.0, (c) 4.8 $\pm$ 0.1, (d) 4.5 $\pm$ 0.1 and the free energies of formation at the same temperature are (a) -6.2 $\pm$ 0.1, (b) -6.0 $\pm$ 0.0, (c) -6.8 $\pm$ 0.1, (d) -6.2 $\pm$ 0.1 kcal. The range of concentrations for adherence to Beer's law, the value of molecular extinction coefficient, and sensitivity of the colour reaction are 0.14-5.6 p.p.m., 10,000, and 0.035 γ /cm², respectively.

Extensive work on the metal chelates of 3''-sulpho-2'', 6''-dichloro-3,3'-dimethyl-4-hydroxyfuchson-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (CAS)^{1,2} has been carried out in these laboratories and their analytical applications have been worked out¹⁻⁴. Munshi and Dey⁵ reported the formation of indium (III) chelate with CAS. In continuation of the same work, it was thought of interest to study the chelate formation of gallium (III) and thallium (III). During preliminary studies it was observed that though boron (III), aluminium (III), gallium (III), and indium (III) yielded coloured chelates with CAS, no chromogenic reaction of thallium (I or III) was observed to take place under identical conditions. The formation of gallium (III)—CAS is being reported for the first time in the present communication along with the composition, nature, and stability of the chelate. Suitable conditions for their micro-determinations have been worked out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Weighted quantities of gallium chloride (Johnson Matthey & Co. Ltd.) were dissolved in acidulated water, estimated by the usual methods, and the solutions suitably diluted as necessary. An aqueous stock solution of Chrome Azurol S (B.D.H. indicator) was prepared and the solutions of the required concentration were obtained by dilution.

A Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer was employed for the measurement of absorbance. All measurements of absorbance were noted against distilled water blanks and 10 mm glass cells were used. At wave lengths of 625 m μ or below, ultrasensitive phototube was used; above this the red-sensitive phototube was used. The phototube circuit was kept at maximum sensitivity.

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1. Dey, *Mikrochim. Acta*, Benedetti-Pichler Anniversary Number, 1964, 414.

2. Srivastava and Dey, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, 25, 217.

3. Munshi and Dey, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 340.

pH of the solutions was measured with a Leeds and Northrup direct-reading pH indicator with a glass-calomel electrode system. All the experiments were carried out in an air-conditioned room maintained at $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. The total volume of the mixtures was kept at 25 ml. The pHs of all the solutions and the mixtures were adjusted to 4.0 ± 0.2 by adding NaOH or HCl; these were then thermostated at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.01^{\circ}$ for about an hour before use.

CAS, like most of the chromophoric dyes, was found to behave as a colloidal electrolyte⁴; hence extremely dilute solutions of the order of 10^{-4} or $10^{-5}M$ were employed for the physico-chemical measurements.

Gallium Chelate

Nature of the Complex Formed.— $\lambda_{\max}$ of the chelate was determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁵. The absorbance values of mixtures in various ratios of the reactants show that only one complex is formed under the conditions of study with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 550 m μ . The $\lambda_{\max}$ of the reagent at this pH is 490 m μ .

Effect of pH.—The $\lambda_{\max}$ of the chelate holds good between pH 3.0 and 5.0 (Fig. 1). This indicates that the chelate is stable within this pH range.

FIG. 1. Variation of $\lambda_{\max}$ with pH.
($c = 40 \times 10^{-5}M$; $p = 1.0$).

FIG. 2
 $\lambda_{\max} = 590 \text{ m}\mu$. c in A to C are 4.0, 2.0, and $1.33 \times 10^{-4}M$ respectively.

Effect of Temperature.—The colour of the chelate did not show any marked change within a wide range of temperature, i.e. $5^{\circ} - 90^{\circ}$.

Stability of Colour at Room Temperature.—The colour of the chelate did not depend on reaction time and assumed its full intensity within less than 5 min.

4. Srivastava et al., *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1962, 17, 86.
5. *J. Amer. chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630.
6. Mukherji and Dey, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.
7. *Idem*, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 18, 324.

Effect of Reagent Concentration.—For determination purposes there should be a 4-fold or greater molar excess of the reagent over gallium concentration.

Composition of the Chelate.—The ratio of gallium to the ligand was measured by the continued variations method⁸, the mole-ratio method⁹, and the slope-ratio method⁹. All the three methods showed the chelate to have 1:1 ratio of gallium to organic ligand (Fig. 2). The results obtained by the method of continued variations, taking equimolecular solutions of metal as well as chelating agent are summarised in Table I (c =concentration of the metal ion, c' =concentration of the reagent, $p=c'/c$).

Adherence to Beer's Law.—The validity of Beer's law was confirmed by measuring the colour intensity of the chelate at pH 4.0 with varying concentrations of gallium chloride in presence of 5-fold excess of the reagent. Beer's law was adhered to over the range of 0.14-5.6 p.p.m. of gallium.

TABLE I

Total volume=25 ml.

Fig.	Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	λ .	Volume of CaCl_2 at peak.	Composition of the chelate. (Ga: CAS).
2	A	4.00M	1.0	580 m μ	12.50 ml	1 : 1
	B	2.00	1.0	580	12.50	1 : 1
	C	1.33	1.0	580	12.50	1 : 1
Not shown	A	4.00	1.0	590	12.50	1 : 1
	B	2.00	1.0	590	12.50	1 : 1
	C	1.33	1.0	590	12.50	1 : 1

Sensitivity.—According to Sandell (based on an absorbance of 0.001 unit), the sensitivity was 0.035 γ/cm^2 at 580 m μ , but the practical sensitivity (based on an absorbance of 0.01 unit) was 0.35 γ/cm^2 .

Molecular Extinction Coefficient.—The molecular extinction coefficient of the gallium-CAS was determined at 580 m μ . The mixtures contained $10.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ of gallium chloride and 10, 13, 15 ml respectively of $2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ solution of the reagent. The molar extinction coefficients, calculated for each solution, were respectively 1.005×10^4 , 1.025×10^4 , and 0.97×10^4 , affording an average of 1.0×10^4 .

Evaluation of Stability Constants.—The stability constants were calculated by four different methods, namely (a) the method of Dey and co-workers^{6,7}, (b) the method of continued variations⁸, (c) the method of mole ratio⁹, and (d) by the measurements of molecular extinction coefficient. The values of change in free energy of formation were also calculated.

For the calculation of K by method (a), concentrations of the metal ions used are shown in Table II. ($p=1$). For method (b), the concentrations and the volume of the metal ion used at the peak are shown in Table III.

8. Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1926, **2**, 9, 113.9. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

TABLE II			TABLE III			Volume of the metal ion used at the peak.
Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	
A	6.07M	1.0	A	3.94M	0.50	6.0
B	5.00	1.0	B	2.50	2.00	11.5
C	4.00	1.0				

For calculation of K by method (c), the concentrations E_M and E_B and α are shown in Table IV.

†Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	E_M .	E_B .	α .
A	1.00M	0.245	0.170	0.30
B	0.66	0.150	0.105	0.30

For calculation of K by method (d), the concentrations and the values of molecular extinction coefficient are recorded Table V.

Total conc. ($c \times 10^4 M$)		Ratio M:Ke.	Absorbance of mixtures.	Concentration ($c \times 10^4 M$) of the Complex.	Concentration ($c \times 10^4 M$) of the Free components.		Mol. extinct. coeff. $\times 10^{-4}$.
M.	Ke.				M.	Ke.	
2.00	2.00	1:1	1.435	1.435	0.565	0.565	1.005
1.00	1.00	1:1	0.600	0.600	0.310	0.310	1.025
0.67	0.67	1:1	0.405	0.405	0.175	0.175	0.970

The values of $\log K$ along with the value of $^* \Delta G^\circ$, as determined by the various methods, are shown in Table VI ($pH=4.0$).

Log K .	ΔG° at 25° (k cal.).	Method.
4.5 $\pm$ 0.1	- 6.2 $\pm$ 0.1	(a)
4.4 $\pm$ 0.0	- 6.0 $\pm$ 0.0	(b)
4.8 $\pm$ 0.1	- 6.8 $\pm$ 0.1	(c)
4.5 $\pm$ 0.1	- 6.2 $\pm$ 0.1	(d)

Suggestions on the Structure of the Chelate.—From the experimental results it is not possible to obtain definite information on the position of the chelate ring, but some tentative suggestions about the structure of the chelate might be made. There are two positions where the chelation might occur. Either the chelation may take place between quinoid oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygens, in which case the chelate would be neutral. On the other hand, chelation between phenolic oxygen and adjacent carboxylic oxygen yields an anionic complex. In the present case, adsorption studies by ion-exchange resin Amberlite IR-45 (OH) (B.D.H. AnalR) has indicated the complex to be anionic.

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* $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$.

† Fig. not shown.